

Self-Diagnosing Tendencies among Senior High School Students

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Abstract

The trend of self-diagnosis, based on the abundance of health-related information available on the internet, has lately been experienced increasingly, especially among young people. Neuroticism, the key personality feature that is expressed as emotional instability and stress susceptibility, may be a factor that affects individuals in their desire to engage in self-diagnosis. This study explores the self-diagnosing tendencies and Neuroticism levels of Marian students from the Senior High School Department. The study conducted is quantitative in nature and used a descriptive research design. This enabled demographic data collection, including gender, sex, grade level strand, and social media usage duration. Results were analyzed using statistical analysis. Results revealed that senior high students have a moderate tendency to self-diagnose using information from social media. Majority of senior high school students have moderate to high levels of neuroticism, showing signs of anxiety, stress, or emotional instability. The correlation analysis between self-diagnosing tendencies and levels of neuroticism reveals a moderately positive relationship with p-value of .0001. A comparison of self-diagnosing tendencies across multiple variables indicated no statistically significant variations according on sex, strand, age, or duration of social media use. However, a statistically significant difference was seen in grade level. For neuroticism levels, statistically significant differences are seen in terms of sex and the duration of social media use. Findings of this study can be used as a basis for contributing knowledge and providing interventions for adolescents who engage in self-diagnosis and social media.

Keywords: adolescents, health-related information, neuroticism, self-diagnosis, social media

Introduction

As the world progresses, the internet has become a significant tool to access information online. Generation Z is the first generation to grow up in a world seamlessly connected by the Internet (Rothman, 2016). News and reviews, including psychological content, are among the different kinds of information Gen Z often turns out to on the Internet through different online platforms such as Facebook, Instagram, Reddit, X (formerly known as Twitter), YouTube, and so on. Queensland Government (2023) states that social media is a form of digital communication on online platforms that let people interact with others and share and create content through communities and that social media communication has many forms, including text, images, videos, sounds, stories, posts, and live streams. Unair, B. (2023) stated in their article that with all the convenience of the Internet that Generation Z has, they could access it whenever and wherever they want. Furthermore, since this health-related information is easily accessible, adolescents' behavior, attitudes, and decisions can be shaped by a high degree of persuasion, potentially impacting their identity and conduct.

Self-Diagnosis

The research study of Stephen, Z. and Ahmend, A. (2017) explains that self-diagnosis is the process of individuals identifying a disease or disorder based on their symptoms without medical consultation. It involves observing and adjusting behavior or dispositional traits to the symptoms. Although the participants' lived experiences with self-diagnosis varied in how they experienced and managed their symptoms, in general, their decision to self-diagnose and ultimately self-medicate is influenced by their internet searches, advice from friends and family, and the lessons learned from previous self-diagnosis experiences (Luis, A. R. et al., 2020).

Neuroticism

One of the core areas of general personality included by the five-factor model, also known as the Big Five, is neuroticism. It is the inclination to feel bad things, such as despair, irritation, self-consciousness, rage, worry, and emotional instability (National Library of Medicine, 2017). It is often defined as a negative personality trait involving negative emotions, poor self-regulation (an inability to manage urges), trouble dealing with stress, a strong reaction to perceived threats, and the tendency to complain.

Research Question

The study aims to explore self-diagnosing tendencies and the neurotic behavior of senior high school students for the academic year 2024-2025. To achieve this, the following questions are asked:

1. What are the demographic profiles of the respondents in terms of:
 - 1) sex;
 - 2) strand;
 - 3) age;
 - 4) grade level and;
 - 5) duration of social media use?
2. What are the self-diagnosing tendencies among senior high school students?
3. What is the level of neuroticism among senior high school students?
4. Is there a significant relationship between the self-diagnosing tendency and the level of neuroticism among students?
5. Is there a significant difference between the self-diagnosing tendency and the level of neuroticism among students when grouped by demographic variables?

Methodology

Research Design

The design of the study followed a quantitative and descriptive-correlational comparative approach in collecting and analyzing self-diagnosing tendencies and neuroticism levels among senior high school students. The researchers selected this approach as it enables the collection of demographic data from the participants, including gender, strand, grade level, self-diagnosis tendency, and duration of social media use. Additionally, a quantitative approach was employed in the questionnaire, facilitating the gathering and quantification of numerical data.

Participants

The research participants were senior high school students from Saint Mary's University Senior High School for the academic year 2024-2025. The students were selected from 6 different strands offered by the school, representing diverse fields: ABM, HUMSS, STEM, TVL ICT, TVL HE, GAS, and AD. Based on the official and latest data gathered from the registrar's office, it was reported that there were 942 senior high school enrollees for the academic year 2024-2025. In determining the actual sample size of this study, Slovin's formula was used, with a 95% confidence level and a margin of error of 0.05. The calculated sample yielded 282 research respondents. Moreover, researchers adjusted to accommodate the gender distribution in some strands. Researchers adjusted the sample size to address the characteristics of the population. The final sample size consisted of 286 research

respondents. With the population presented, proportionate sampling was employed across the 7 strands (STEM n=200, HUMSS n= 38, ABM n=28, GAS n=0, TVL-ICT n=8, TVL-HE n=6, and AD n=6)

Instruments of the Study

The instrument used in this study consisted of informed consent, which provided sufficient information regarding respondents' participation, and demographic questions, which identified respondents' sex, strand, age, grade level, and duration of social media use. Moreover, two standardized tools were utilized: Level of Neuroticism adopted from the Enhanced 2020 version of The Big Five Personality Test (B5T)(Satow, L. in 2020.), and Self-Diagnosing Tendency which the researchers developed. The instrument of this study was administered face-to-face in each respondent's respective classrooms by their class advisers.

Procedure

This research studied the levels of neuroticism, the self-diagnosing tendency among senior high school students, and their correlation. The researchers explored a variety of tools that are best to measure the participants' level of neuroticism and self-diagnosing tendency. The tools utilized were carefully chosen based on their psychometric properties and appropriateness. Additionally, the instruments used were pilot-tested to ensure reliability further.

The collection of data began after the University Research Ethics Board (UREB) and the University Research Center (URC) of SMU thoroughly reviewed and provided clearance in conducting this study. The researchers wrote an official request letter to the Principal of Saint Mary's University Senior High School (SMU SHS) to request permission to conduct a pilot test. After approval, the researchers coordinated with the class advisers to disseminate the information. After analyzing the pilot test results, researchers wrote another letter to the principal asking permission to administer the research questionnaires to the students. The instrument contained informed consent and two standardized tools. The questionnaires were administered face-to-face in each respondent's respective classrooms by their class advisers. Class advisers collected the questionnaires and submitted them to the research coordinator. The researchers subsequently retrieved the questionnaires. After collecting the questionnaires, IBM SPSS version 21 was used extensively and accurately to analyze the data.

Results

Demographic Profile of the Respondents

This section shows the respondents' demographic profiles in terms of sex, strand, age, grade level, and duration of social media use with the use of descriptive statistics.

Table 1
Profile of the Respondents

Variables	Categories	f(n=286)	%
Sex	Male	146	51.0
	Female	140	49.0
Strand	Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics Strand (STEM)	200	69.9
	Humanities and Social Sciences Strand (HUMSS)	38	13.3
	Accountancy, Business and Management Strand (ABM)	28	9.8
	General Academic Strand (GAS)	0	0
	Technical Vocational and Livelihood Information and Communication Technology Strand (TVL ICT)	8	2.8
	Technical Vocational and Livelihood Home Economics Strand (TVL HE)	6	2.1
	Arts and Design Strand (AD)	6	2.1
Age	15 years old	5	1.7
	16 years old	130	45.5
	17 years old	136	47.6
	18 years old	15	5.2
Grade Level	Grade 11	138	48.3
	Grade 12	148	51.7
Duration of Social Media Use	Less than 2 hours	14	4.9
	2-5 hours	134	46.9
	More than 5 hours	138	48.3

Self-Diagnosing Tendencies

This section presents the quantitative summary of the senior high students' self-diagnosing tendency.

Table 2
The Self-Diagnosing Tendencies Among Senior High School Students

n=286	Low Inclination Towards Self-Diagnosis		Moderate Inclination Towards Self-Diagnosis		High Inclination Towards Self-Diagnosis		\bar{x}	SD
	f	%	f	%	f	%		
Self-Diagnosing Tendencies	42	14.7	190	66.4	54	18.9	39.209	7.728

Qualitative Description: 15-30(Low Inclination Towards Self-Diagnosis); 31-45(Moderate Inclination Towards Self-Diagnosis); 46-60(High Inclination Towards Self-Diagnosis)

Level of Neuroticism among Senior High School Students

This section presents the quantitative summary of the senior high students' level of neuroticism.

Table 3
Level of Neuroticism

	Low Neuroticism		Moderate Neuroticism		High Neuroticism		\bar{x}	SD
	f	%	f	%	f	%		
n=286								
Level of Neuroticism	40	14.0	91	31.8	155	54.2	30.080	6.784

Qualitative Description: 10-20(Low Neuroticism); 21-30(Moderate Neuroticism); 31-40(High Neuroticism)

Relationship Between the Dependent Variables

This section presents the quantitative summary of the relationship between senior high students' self-diagnosing tendency and level of neuroticism.

Table 4
Relationship Between Self-Diagnosing Tendency and Level of Neuroticism

		Self-Diagnosing Tendencies	Neuroticism
Self-Diagnosing Tendencies	Spearman ρ	1.00	.445
	p-value		.0001
Neuroticism	Spearman ρ	.445	1.00
	p-value	.0001	

Comparison of the Respondents' Level of Self-diagnosing Tendencies and Level of Neuroticism in terms of Demographic Profiles

This section presents the quantitative summary of the differences of self-diagnosing tendencies and level of neuroticism when grouped according to sex, strand, age, grade level, and duration of social media use.

Table 5
Summary of Respondents' Self-Diagnosing Tendency When Grouped Demographic By Variables

	Sex	Strand	Grade Level	Age	Duration of Social Media Use
Self-Diagnosing Tendency	.5280	.0910	.4110	.0310	.6650

Table 6
Summary of Respondents' Level Of Neuroticism When Grouped Demographic By Variables

	Sex	Strand	Grade Level	Age	Duration of Social Media Use
Level of Neuroticism	.0001	.8600	.8300	.0840	.0001

Discussion

The research respondents comprised a total population of 286 senior high school students, with a nearly equal distribution in terms of sex because it was attributed to the nature of the population's distribution rather than the intended sampling. The majority of the academic strands came from the Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics (STEM) strand, Humanities and Social Sciences (HUMSS) strand, Accountancy, Business, and Management (ABM) strand, General Academic Strand (GAS) has no respondents to represent since no students enrolled in this strand, Technical Vocational and Livelihood Information and Communication Technology (TVL ICT) strand, Technical Vocational and Livelihood Home Economics (TVL HE) strand, and the Arts and Design strand. Regarding the ages, the age range of the respondents is from 15 – 18 years old but the majority are between the ages of 16 to 17. In terms of grade level, the distribution is nearly equal based on the distribution of the population. Social media usage suggests that the majority spend more than 5 hours daily and these findings show that social media is integrated into senior high school students' lives, and many spend a significant proportion of their leisure time on these platforms.

The study found that there is a moderate level of self-diagnosing tendencies among senior high school students and it suggests that they actively seek health-related information online, try to interpret their symptoms, and conclude their findings with a diagnosis. While this behavior may reflect a concern for their health, sometimes, it may lead to more significant anxiety as they might be able to misinterpret symptoms and even assume worst-case scenarios. This is in line with the study of Gonzales et al. (2019), in which 110 students believed that they were at risk of having a mental health problem, and 76 stated that their primary concern was anxiety. Students reported feelings linked with anxiety, which include persistent worrying, agitation, and inability to focus. While their efforts are aimed at addressing their concerns, this sometimes might lead to an inaccurate diagnosis and even more stress.

In terms of their level of neuroticism, it is generally moderate. Since the majority of students fall within the moderate neuroticism range, this suggests that a significant portion of the senior high school population may experience anxiety, stress, and emotional instability. These findings align with the study by Cruz et al. (2021), which reported that senior high school students have average neuroticism scores of 3.18, indicating high levels of neuroticism. The study also highlighted that students tend to exhibit negative emotional states, such as worry, fear, and heightened sensitivity. The data further imply that a moderate level of neuroticism can impact mental health and academic performance. In the study by Fuente and Sander (2022), a negative correlation was observed between neuroticism and academic confidence. Students with higher neuroticism levels were found to feel less confident in their academic abilities, negatively affecting their well-being and performance. These students often experience more negative emotions related to their studies and have an increased susceptibility to stress. This highlights that high levels of neuroticism can hinder students' motivation, academic success, and overall performance, worsening challenges in the academic setting.

In terms of the relationship between Self-Diagnosing Tendency and level of neuroticism, there is a moderate positive correlation between these two variables. This means that as people become more neurotic, they are more likely to start diagnosing themselves as well. People with higher neuroticism are more likely to perceive themselves as having some psychological or physical ailment. Moreover, Kaspar and Müller-Jensen (2021) reported that neuroticism has a positive connection with information-seeking on Facebook. People with high neuroticism are more likely to follow the accounts of others to gain information.

The comparison of respondents' self-diagnosing tendency in terms of sex using the Mann-Whitney U test revealed that the observed difference between males and females is not statistically significant. This indicates that there is no significant difference in self-diagnosing tendency based on sex. Ybarra and Suman's study (2008, as cited in Luo et al., 2022) shows that there is a potential for differences in the utilization of the Internet for health information searching based on sex and age. The results showed that both genders most often used the Internet to seek information on the health state of a close one. However, when it comes to overall internet usage for seeking health information, no gender differences were observed. The research evidence indicates that self-diagnosing activity may not be affected by sex.

In terms of strands in self-diagnosing tendency, results show that there is no significant difference in the self-diagnosing tendencies of the students across strands. Thus, it suggests that the strand is a negative predictor of self-diagnosing tendency. In terms of age from 15-18 years old, it shows that age does not significantly influence the self-diagnosing tendencies of senior high school students. This is supported by the study by Ginting E. and Hati P. (2023), which indicates that when young people, in general, feel they are experiencing mental health problems, they can easily search for and access information through the Internet. In terms of grade level, it influences self-diagnosing tendencies. This is supported by the findings of the research of Gonzales, M.V. et al. (2019), wherein 110 out of 189 of their senior high school student participants perceive themselves as at risk of having mental health issues through self-diagnosis. When it comes to their social media usage duration, self-diagnosing tendency signifies no statistically significant difference in self-diagnosing tendencies based on the duration of social media use. This indicates that despite prolonged social media exposure, it does not necessarily result in high self-diagnosing tendencies and vice versa.

On the other hand, the comparison of respondents' level of neuroticism in terms of sex suggests that females are more sensitive to unpleasant emotions and this shows that gender plays a significant role in the level of neuroticism. This is supported by DeYoung et al. (2011) have revealed that higher scores in neuroticism characterize women in comparison with men. The findings suggest that women who have high neuroticism are due to biological components. This is in concordance with the study done by Djudiyah et al. (2016) on the relationship between hormonal functions and mood and personality.

While respondent's level of neuroticism in terms of age, it shows that there is no statistically significant difference in neuroticism levels among the strands. In terms of age, there is also no significant difference in the neuroticism level between the different age groups. This implies that age is not enough for neuroticism to occur. In terms of grade level, suggests that there is no significant difference in terms of the level of neuroticism between grade 11 and grade 12. However, this contradicts the findings of Dizon, M. (2022), where neuroticism as a personality trait showed a significant difference in terms of grade level. When it comes to their social media usage duration, data shows that there is a statistically significant difference in their level of neuroticism. This means prolonged social media use is associated with higher neuroticism levels, suggesting that excessive engagement may amplify emotional instability. The study of Zubair et al. (2023) found that excessive social media use is linked to mental health issues such as anxiety, depression, and stress, with these effects worsening as usage time and platform variety increase.

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